

**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER'S SATISFACTION TOWARDS
RELIANCE JIO 4G DATA SERVICE (WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO POLLACHI TALUK)**

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Cite This Article: Dr. S. Shanmugapriya & M. Sangeetha, "A Study on Customer's Satisfaction towards Reliance Jio 4G Data Service (With Special Reference to Pollachi Taluk)", *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education*, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 156-159, 2018.

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Abstract:

A computer network or a data network is a digital telecommunication network which allows to provide resources of Reliance Jio limited (RJL) a subsidiary of Reliance Industry Limited (RIL) is India's largest private sector company, which is the most first telecom operator to hold pan India unified license. The company provides all communications services except global mobile personal communication by satellite services. The objective of this study is to know the socio economic profile of sample users and to identify customer's satisfaction level of Reliance JIO 4G data service. In this study the Questionnaire method is used to collect the data the simple percentage and chi-square method is applied. The major findings of this study and suitable suggestions are presented in this article.

Key Words: Customer's Satisfaction, Telecommunication & Service

Introduction:

India is one of the world's largest telecom markets which is particularly in the field of mobile internet due to the most high population and development. There are Airtel, Vodafone, Idea, Telenor India, Reliance, Jio, Tata DoCoMo, BSNL, Aircel, Tata Indicom are the major operators in the world. The telephony was introduced by 1882. Indian telecom operators are 227.27 million wireless subscribers in the 12 months between March 2010 and March 2011 averaging at 18.94 million subscribers every month. Currently China is the world's largest telecommunications network added 119.2 million wireless subscribers during the same period. The telephone wireless and landline subscribers are 1058.01 million on May 2016. Most importantly the next phase of growth of 4G services is to the wireless segment with enhanced focus on providing data services of the internet. Whereas the Reliance Jio Infocomm Ltd ("RJIL") and Reliance Communications Limited ("RCOM") announced the signing of Agreements for Change in Spectrum Allotment in 800 MHz band across 9 Circles from RCOM to RJIL, and for Sharing of Spectrum in 800 MHz band across 17 Circles. Where Reliance Jio has announced the record of network has been created a world record by crossing 16 million in total subscribers during the first month of operation. The Reliance Jio Company currently have 52 to 55 million subscribers using Jio 4G service. Reliance Jio provides the services as secured and safety way and the internet to satisfy the customers to their offers and discount packages. Whereas Reliance Communications has established a pan-India, next generation, integrated (wireless and wire line), convergent (voice, data and video) digital network that is capable for supporting best-of-class services spanning the entire communications value chain and covering all over 21,000 cities and towns and also over 400,000 villages. World's largest communication the next generation IP enabled connectivity of infrastructure comprising over 280,000 kilometers of fibre optic cable systems in India.

Review of Literature:

C. Boobalan et al (2017) in their study on, "customer's satisfaction towards Reliance JIO sim with special reference to Dharmapuri District" made an attempt to know the satisfaction level of multi customers. Most of the customers are selecting Reliance JIO as it comes under for sim cards are free and most of the customers for understanding the income and satisfaction level of JIO services is comes under between (10001-20000). Finally conclude that most of the customers are satisfied with the current JIO services. K. R. Mahalaxmi and N. Suresh Kumar (2017) in this article titled, "A study on service quality and its impact on customer's preference and satisfaction towards Reliance JIO in trichy region" focus on to the service quality and satisfaction level of Reliance JIO. This study reveals that peoples with age group up to 35 were 78 per cent users of Reliance JIO. The advertisement has motivates most of the customers to prefer this network. Dr. Gowthamichintala et al (2017) in this article entitled, "customers satisfaction towards telecommunication service provider-A study on Reliance JIO" is to know the satisfaction level of the customers. The gender wise analysis of the customers satisfaction is conclude that there is no difference in the opinion of male and female respondents on the satisfaction level towards the service provided by the JIO services.

Statement of the Problem:

Essentially, good quality at cheaper cost and few value added service and sincere service with smile when you are in trouble: these are what excellent data service is all about. There are various data service provider in our country and they are playing an essential role fulfilling the needs of the customers. Just like any other services industry in India, it is very difficult to refer any 4G data service provider as “The Best”. But we can find a best one after conducting a brief study. The success of the service provider’s dependence upon the customer’s satisfaction. Hence an attempt has been made to study the customer satisfaction towards Reliance Jio 4G data a service in Pollachi Taluk.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out the solution for the above problems, the present study has been under taken with the following objectives. There are

- ✓ To know the socio-economic profile of sample users.
- ✓ To ascertain the preference level of the customers regarding the services provided in 4G data service.
- ✓ To identify customers satisfaction level of Reliance Jio 4G data service in study area.

Research Methodology:

The present study is mainly based on primary data and secondary data collection by distributing the questionnaire to the users residing in Pollachi Taluk. The questionnaire contains questions relating to the personal profile of the users, preferences and satisfaction of users towards Reliance Jio 4G data service. Necessary guidance was given to the respondents for filling up the questionnaire.

Sample Design:

The study is concerned with the customer of Reliance Jio 4G data service. Of the total 120 questionnaires issued, 115 questionnaires are collected and out of the 115 questionnaires collected, 112 questionnaires are taken for analysis because of incomplete information found in the 3 questionnaires. Convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sample users.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent
Area of Residence		
Rural	47	41.96
Urban	37	33.04
Semi-Urban	28	25
Age		
Up to 25 years	45	40.18
26-40 years	24	21.43
41-50 years	32	28.57
Above 50 years	11	9.82
Gender		
Male	68	60.71
Female	44	39.29
Marital status		
Married	48	42.86
Unmarried	64	57.14
Educational qualification		
Up to HSC	0	0
Under Graduate	62	55.36
Post Graduate	36	42.86
Professionals	14	12.50
Occupation		
Employee agriculture	26	23.21
Agriculture	18	16.10
Professionals	14	12.49
Business	23	20.53
Students	31	27.67
Type of family		
Joint	58	51.79
Nuclear	54	48.21
Size of the family		
Two	36	32.14
Three	27	24.12

Four	39	34.82
Above four	10	8.93
Earning members in the family		
One	34	30.36
Two	72	64.28
Three	6	5.36
Above three	-	-
Monthly income of the family		
Up to 50000	65	58.04
50001-100000	37	33.03
100000-300000	10	8.93
Above 300000	-	-

Out of the total 112 respondents, 33.04 % belong to urban area, 25 % belong to semi-urban area and the rest 41.96 % belong to rural area. Hence, it is said that most of the respondents belong to the rural area. Out of 112 respondents, 40.18 % belong to the age group of up to 25 years, 21.43 % belong to the age group between 26-40 years, 28.57 % belongs to the age group between 41-55 years and 9.82 % belongs to above 55 years. Thus the majority of the respondents belong to the age group up to 25 years. Out of the total 112 respondents, 60.71 % are male and the rest 39.29 % are females. Hence, it is said that majority of the JIO 4G users are male. Out of 112 respondents, 42.86 % are married and the remaining 57.14 % are unmarried. Hence, it is said that most of the JIO 4G users are unmarried. Out of the 112 respondents, 55.36 % are under graduate, 32.14 % are post graduate and remaining 12.50 % are with professional qualification. This shows that majority of the respondents are under graduates. Out of the 112 respondents, 23.21 % are employees, 16.10 % are agriculture, 12.49 % are professional, 20.53 % are business men and remaining 27.67 % are students. Hence, it is observed that most of the respondents are student. Out of the total 112 respondents, 51.79 % belong to joint family and the rest 48.21 % belong to nuclear family. Thus the majority of JIO 4G respondents belong to joint family. Out of the 112 respondents, 32.14 % have two members in their family, 24.12 % have three members in the family, 34.82 % have four members in their family and remaining 8.93 % have above four members in their family. Hence, it is said that most of the respondents have four members in their family. The above table disclose that out of the 112 respondents, 30.36 % have one earning members in their family, 64.28 % have two earning members in their family and remaining 5.36 % have three earning members in their family. Hence, it is said that majority of the respondents have two earning members in their family. Out of the 112 respondents 58.04 % earn up to Rs.50,000 per month, 33.03 % of the respondents family earning per month is between Rs.50,001-1,00,000 and remaining 8.93 % earnings per months between Rs.1,00,001-3,00,000 and none of the family earn above Rs.3,00,000. Hence, it is said that majority of the respondents family earning per month is Up to 50,000.

Chi-Square Analysis:

The chi-square test is very important test to the several statistical techniques for analyzing the significant variables. Whereas here the independent variables namely area of residence, age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, types of the family, members in the family, no of earning members in the family, monthly income have been selected in order to test if there really exist any association between each of the variable and level of satisfaction on JIO 4G Data Service.

Table 2: Selected Variables and Level of Satisfaction on Jio 4G Network

Variables	Chi-Square Value	DF	Table Value 5 Percent Level
Area of Residence	3.666*	4	9.488
Age	7.580	6	13.48
Gender	0.985*	2	5.991
Marital status	0.126*	2	5.991
Educational qualification	8.663*	4	9.488
occupation	6.040*	8	15.507
Types of family	5.991*	2	9.210
No. of members in the family	4.340*	6	12.592
Earning members in the family	10.789*	4	9.488
Monthly income of the family	10.976*	4	9.488

The above table 2 discloses that out the total ten variables selected, nine variables are found to be significant with the consumer's level of satisfaction on JIO 4G network data service. Of them nine variables namely area of residence, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, types of the family, no of members in the family, no of earning members in the family, monthly income of the family are significantly associated with the consumers level of satisfaction at the five per cent level.

Findings:

Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Users:

- The major findings of the study are summarized as follows, there are
- ✓ Most of the respondents, 47(41.96%) belong to rural areas.
 - ✓ Most of the respondents, 45(40.18%) belong to the age group of up to 25 years.
 - ✓ Majority of 68(60.71%) the respondents are male.
 - ✓ Majority of 64(57.14%) the JIO users are unmarried.
 - ✓ Majority of 62(55.36%) the respondents are under graduates.
 - ✓ Most of the respondents, 31(27.67%) occupation are students.
 - ✓ Majority of 58(51.79%), the respondents are joint family.
 - ✓ Most of the respondents, 39(34.82%) have four members in their family.
 - ✓ Majority of 72(64.28%) the respondents have two earning members in their family.
 - ✓ Majority of 65(58.04%) the respondents family monthly income is up to Rs.50000

Suggestion:

Based on the findings of the study and opinion given by JIO 4G data service users at the time of data collection, the following suggestions are put forth. Strength of the signal level of JIO 4G data service of rural area should be increased. Processing speed should be increased. Customer stay with the availability of Value Added Service among the good network coverage. JIO should offer long term loyalty benefits staggered over period of time. Customer care is an important area and produce direct impact on customer satisfaction. In the highly competitive set-up, progressing out of special discount offer or a special value added pack could help to win back the subscriber.

Conclusion:

The analysis exposed that there is a considerable percentage of awareness prevailing among the customers about the service of JIO 4G data service. There are some additional factors which affect quality of service. This of customer awareness, launch of service by new operators, attractive/aggressive tariff plans, innovative services, vas offering, time to resolve disputes etc., in India, several new operators are entering the market and the market and monthly addition of new subscriber is still very high. Also customers play a very vital role in successful delivery of service as customers are often present at the place where service is as per customer defined specifications. Other customers who are present at the time of service can also influence the service positively or negatively. Consumer's preference and satisfaction is the measuring scale of creditability of the service provided by any organization. Internet service providers are not exceptions to it. This research study gives an opportunity to get the feedback of the customers regarding their satisfaction level about the service offered by the service providers.

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